

THE ART OF ORATORY IS THE IMPORTANCE OF SPEECH, THE POWER OF WORDS.

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ABSTRACT: This article focuses on the formation and development of the art of public speaking, how to make the speech attractive and understandable, and what methods to use in the application of this process. The further development of these methods, learned from the works of our scholars, is covered in this article.

KEY WORDS: eloquence, word, skill, ability, talent, speech, enunciation, wit, insight, rhetoric, sophist

Currently, as in the neighboring countries, it is a national goal to create the science of public speaking in a national spirit, based on national values, and to achieve that this subject is taught as a separate philological subject in higher and secondary special educational institutions of our republic. It is one of the important tasks facing spiritual enthusiasts. The art of public speaking is, first of all, a field aimed at forming the existing ability and talent of the speaker, and it is a science that studies and forms the ability and talent of the speaker.

The main task of the art of public speaking is to teach the rules of motivation to be a public speaker. However, not everyone is eloquent. For this, the future speaker must have the ability and talent. Because it is art. That is why some speakers, knowing the material in depth, cannot convey their thoughts with free speech, and as a result, the audience may not understand it. The listeners understand the speech of skilled speakers well and understand the content faster. Oratory should act as the main weapon of ideological struggle. It is an important requirement of today that the art of public speaking is more sharp and sharp than ever. The people who raised this art to the level of a literary genre for the first time and had a scientific approach to public speaking were considered sophists. They create the science of "Rstorika" by starting the theoretical justification of the activities of the speakers who passed before them. First, the orators were called "Rhetor", and then the former teachers of the art of speaking were called "Rhetors". The island of Sicily is the original homeland of rhetoric. It became a factor for the establishment of democracy and the development of oratory in those places by the middle of the 5th century. The ancient Greeks recognized the

Sicilian Corach and Tisylami as the founders of rhetoric, of whom almost nothing has survived. However, their countryman, the sophist Gorgias (ca. 483-376), was considered the first exponent of rhetoric. According to Gorgias, the most important task of the orator is to convince the listener, to charm him, to make him fall in love. It is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the information we give is the most important of these thoughts of Gorgias. wants to show examples of "beautiful" style in his works. The development of the art of speaking led to the formation of the literary language, as well as the emergence of the science of "rhetoric", which is the theory of the art of speaking.

Aristotle's ideas are also an important tool for the development of public speaking. Aristotle teaches mastering the art of public speaking in 5 parts.

1. Discovery of material (comprehensive preparation).
2. Material layout form (plan).
3. Remembering (mastering) the material.
4. The material should be correctly reflected using words.
5. Correct pronunciation of the material.

Aristotle's ideas still hold their value today. Love for the country will also have a great influence on the development of the art of public speaking. A vivid example of this can be found in the life of Cicero. Like most of the wordsmiths of Cicero's time, in the early stages of his career, he paid great attention to the beauty of the style, the liveliness of the phrases, and the elegance of the sentence. Expulsion from the country will be very difficult for Cicero. Only after a year and a half, thanks to the help of his friends, he will be allowed to return to Italy. Endless love for Motherland inspires the great orator. He begins to work tirelessly on the theory of speech. Soon after, as a result of hard work, his three-volume work entitled "On Orators" was published. This work is written in the form of a dialogue and contains the social and political speeches of Lycinius, Crocus, Mark Antony, Julius Caesar, Strabo, Catullus, the jurist Stsevola and his students Catt, Sulnicus Rufus, their oratory and the smallest details of this art. It includes opinions from petty issues to political issues. According to Cicero, an orator should be not just a law-abiding person who knows all the rules of court cases, but a statesman who has a deep understanding of state affairs and can sympathize with the people's grief. Therefore, everyone who is interested in the art of public speaking should not be limited to the primitive knowledge of the science of "Rhetoric" and should not rely on his natural talent, he should always study various disciplines, the highest level of science and culture. it is necessary to aspire to its heights. In addition, the author of "On Speakers" said that speakers should be able to instill fear, anger and

sadness in people's hearts, and on the contrary, they should be able to free people from such exciting situations and awaken feelings of calmness and compassion in their souls. emphasizes. In his opinion, an orator will never be able to achieve his goal if he does not perceive the different characters of people, if he does not know the general characteristics of human nature and if he does not understand the reasons that sometimes disturb and sometimes calm each person. In order not to bore the listener, during the speech, the upbeat method should be lowered a bit, if there are persons related to the topic of the speech, give a negative and sometimes positive characteristic of the person, mention some anecdote about the famous breeds that have passed before, if necessary It was one of Cicero's favorite ways to remember life scenes, dramatic events, and use a wise word, a proverb, or a joke instead. If every orator takes these methods as his first rule, he can certainly reach the peak of eloquence.

We should also remember the thoughts of Beruni, one of the scholars of the East, to improve the art of oratory. Beruni states that there are two types of speech, prose and verse. These types of speech are formed based on certain rules. Prose is written according to the rules of Nahv, Nazm Aruz. Nahv has a wider scope than Aruz, it is necessary for both prose and verse. Beruni writes: "Nahv in prose and Aruz nazm have become two precise criteria that measure the standard and correct the error of the spoken word, but nahv is the more general of the two, because it includes both nasmi and nazm together covers". Thinkers Yusuf Khos Hajib and Ahmad Yugnakiy of the 12th and 13th centuries also gave instructive opinions on the value of the word, its use, giving more meaning by saying less, thinking clearly. The great poet Yusuf Khos Hajib about the correct choice and use of words in the work "Kutadgu Bilig" ("Knowledge that Brings Happiness"), a wonderful artistic monument of the Turkic peoples from the 12th century: "Knowing speaks word knowledge counts." The purpose of speaking is to accurately and effectively convey what the speaker intends to the listener. So, the speaker should not only understand the information he gives, but also know how to convey it. Only then is he considered to have followed the standards of public speaking. Alisher Navoi's work can be compared to the sea. There are countless gems in it, and we can conclude from the great thinker's thoughts on speech, speech and the art of public speaking. Since a great scholar like Navoi paid so much attention to the power of words, we should not forget that our duty is not to read and listen to his thoughts, but to follow him as much as we can. Most importantly, Alisher Navoi pays attention to the use of each word in its proper place. We can learn how wide-ranging the art of public speaking is from the opinions of our scholars above. Anyone who speaks is an orator. His first task is to be able to deliver the text he is talking about. For this, it is

necessary to conclude from the above points and follow them when entering the auditorium.

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